

Master in Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Automatic harmonic analysis of classical string quartets from symbolic score

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Dedication

Grandmother, Juan Rodrigo. Family. Kinga.

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Abstract

This work proposes running an automatic harmonic analysis over a novell dataset of String Quartets from Joseph Haydn. Using implementation code from David Temperley, Daniel Sleator and Craig Sapp. Additionally, proposes an evaluation method to measure the similarity of the resulting analyses against manual annotations included in the String Quartet dataset. 24 musical scores analyzed and evaluated with a range of 15% to 85% accuracy for the Temperley algorithm.

Keywords: Automatic harmonic analysis; Joseph Haydn; String quartet; Roman numeral analysis

Chapter 1

Introduction

In the traditional sense, harmonic analysis relates to a set of music theory studies that pretend to describe the relationship of simultaneous sonorities and generalize rules of how each of these sonorities should move to facilitate and embellish their combined sound.

1.1 Motivation

Students at conservatoires often learn the guidelines of harmonic analysis during a specialized course of Harmony. Such a course could extend to several years, making it a difficult subject to be learnt fast for a beginner. Even in the case of experts, it might take relatively long time to analyze a piece of music in terms of harmony, which makes the task of automating it valuable even for the expert theorist.

It is difficult, however, to give a precise definition of what is harmonic analysis and where the task of automatic harmonic analysis begins and ends. As will be discussed in chapter 3, different researchers have made different characterizations of the problem, sometimes binding these characterizations closely to the mathematical tools they have used to approach the problem, in other cases to the type of music that they pretend to analyze, and in other cases due to other circumstances. For this particular work, I intend to define harmonic analysis based in two simple definitions,

and afterwards, the outcome definition will help to describe which are the expected inputs and outputs of an automatic harmonic analysis system.

1.2 Harmonic analysis

According to the Oxford Music Online dictionary, in the context of music, the term *analysis* could be defined as the following: [1]

*[...] the interpretation of structures in music,
their resolution into relatively simpler constituent elements,
and the investigation of the relevant functions of those elements.*

Additionally, according to the same source, a very simplistic definition of harmony could be: [2]

The simultaneous sounding (i.e. combination) of notes [...]

Menuetto: Allegretto

Harmony

The image shows a musical score for a Minuet in G major, Op. 20 No. 3 by Joseph Haydn. It features four staves: Violin I, Violin II, Viola, and Violoncello. The music is in 3/4 time. A red rectangular box highlights the first measure of the second system, where all four instruments play simultaneously, illustrating the concept of harmony as the simultaneous sounding of notes.

Figure 1: Excerpt from Joseph Haydn's Op.20 No.3 - II. Menuetto: Allegretto, mm. 1-6

Combining these definitions, one possible interpretation of what is a harmonic analysis could be the following:

[...] the interpretation of **harmonic** structures in music, their resolution into relatively simpler constituent elements, *i.e.*, **harmonic labels**, and the investigation of the relevant functions of those **labels**.

Menuetto: Allegretto

Harmonic structures

The image shows a musical score for a Minuet in G minor, Allegretto. It features four staves: Violin I, Violin II, Viola, and Violoncello. The key signature has two flats (B-flat and E-flat), and the time signature is 3/4. Red vertical boxes are drawn across the staves, highlighting specific harmonic structures. These structures are vertical alignments of notes from different instruments that occur at the same time, representing chords or harmonic moments. The boxes are placed at the beginning of measures 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9.

Figure 2: Highlighting harmonic structures in musical excerpt

Therefore, as stated by this definition, the process of harmonic analysis comprises three steps:

- Interpret harmonic structures
- Resolve them into harmonic labels
- Investigate their relevant functions

For breaking down the steps of the analysis, we could use a fragment of a musical score. Figure 1 remarks the first beat of the second measure, where three instruments play notes together. Every instance of these simultaneities represents harmony. If these harmonies are clustered and interpreted, we come up with harmonic structures, as in Figure 2.

In order to satisfy the second step of harmonic analysis, we could resolve this interpretation of harmonic structures into some sort of simpler representation. Historically, music theorists performing these sort of harmonic analysis will most likely

come with a system of labels that represent the meaning of the harmonic structures. There is not a single labeling system for this purpose. Figure 3 shows three possible representations for the harmonic structures of the same music excerpt presented previously.

Menuetto: Allegretto

Chord Labels	Gm	A ^{dim}	Gm/Bb	Cm	Gm/Bb	F ^{#dim} /A	F ^{#dim} 7/A	Dm/A
Figured Bass	b5	6	5	6	#6	#6 5 3	#6 4 3	
Roman Numerals	i	ii ^o	i6	iv	i6	vii ^o 6	vii ^o 5	V3

Figure 3: Three different harmonic labeling representations of a musical fragment

Any of these three representations would suffice the second step of harmonic analysis. The chord labels in the first representation are what is commonly seen to label harmonic structures in jazz and pop music. The figured bass from the second representation was very popular previous to the classical period, and it was intended to aid accompanists who played in chamber ensembles, e.g., it helped a harpsichordist to "fill-in" the accompaniment during the performance when only one note was given in the score. The third representation using roman numerals emerged previously but consolidated with the theoretical work of Hugo Riemann, and its purpose is mainly of analysis. For this work, I have selected to use the third kind of representation, because it is the one that helps the better in the third step of the process, *specifying the function of the harmonic labels*.

In fact, it could be claimed that in the roman numeral labels themselves, the whole process of harmonic analysis gets summarized, as the clustering and interpretation

of harmonic structures will be characterized by the appearance of harmonic labels, and in the case of roman numeral labels, the function of that harmonic structure is implicitly given by the roman numeral degree.

1.3 Automatic harmonic analysis

Once the steps in the process of performing a harmonic analysis and the selected labels for harmonic structures are specified, I will now define a system of automatic harmonic analysis as a piece of software that given a fragment of music as input, will output the same piece of music, with roman numeral labels appended to it, as Figure 4 shows.

Figure 4: A system of automatic harmonic analysis

There is, however, the problem of choosing among the multiple ways in which this score can be represented. For this work, a symbolic representation in the *humdrum* [3] format was chosen as the input format for this system. Similarly, the output consists of the same humdrum representation with an additional spine in the ***harm* [4] syntax. The justification behind this decision will be described in chapter 2.

Chapter 2

Dataset

The dataset used for this work is a novel dataset created as part of the final output of this work. It consists of 24 musical scores corresponding to six string quartets, Op.20, written by Joseph Haydn. These quartets are commonly known as the *Sun quartets*.

The comprehensive works included in Op.20 is listed in Table 1. Among the 24 pieces of these string quartets we can find interesting scenarios to perform harmonic analyses, some of them in terms of musical structure, e.g., sonata form and minuet; some other in terms of texture and compositional craft, e.g., fugue and melody and accompaniment. This variety of musical contexts was one important reason to create a harmonic analysis dataset out of these string quartets.

The dataset lies in the following repository https://github.com/napulen/haydn_op20_harm.

2.1 String quartet

String quartets are one of the most prominent genres developed during the Classical period. For composing in this genre, a broad knowledge of harmony is required.

In terms of harmonic analysis, string quartets are interesting as they provide four voices for most of the time, which is the number of voices in which harmony is usually

Number	Movement	Tempo	Musical form
Op.20 No.1			
1	I	Allegro Moderato	Sonata
2	II	Minuetto. Allegretto	Minuet
3	III	Affettuoso e sostenuto	Aria
4	IV	Finale. Presto	Allegro
Op.20 No.2			
5	I	Moderato	Sonata
6	II	Adagio	Aria*
7	III	Minuetto. Allegretto	Minuet
8	IV	Fuga a 4 Soggetti	Fuga
Op.20 No.3			
9	I	Allegro con Spirito	Sonata
10	II	Minuetto. Allegretto	Minuet
11	III	Poco Adagio	Aria
12	IV	Finale. Allegro Molto	Sonata
Op.20 No.4			
13	I	Allegro di Molto	Sonata
14	II	Un poco Adagio Affettuoso	Theme and variations
15	III	Allegretto alla zingarese	Minuet
16	IV	Presto scherzando	Sonata
Op.20 No.5			
17	I	Allegro moderato	Sonata
18	II	Minuetto	Minuet
19	III	Adagio	Siciliana
20	IV	Finale: Fuga a due Soggetti	Fuga
Op.20 No.6			
21	I	Allegro di Molto e Scherzando	Sonata
22	II	Adagio, Cantabile	Sonata
23	III	Minuetto. Allegretto	Minuet
24	IV	Fuga a 3 Soggetti. Allegro	Fuga

Table 1: The 24 music pieces within Haydn's Op.20

taught and studied. Additionally, in the symbolic representation of the music, it is more likely that each voice will be separated in a different channel or medium, which is an additional aid to the harmonic analysis algorithms, as melodic segregation is an important problem seen in these algorithms.

2.2 Joseph Haydn

Joseph Haydn is colloquially named *The father of the string quartet*. He represents a major figure of the classical period of western art music, exemplifying many of the characteristic features of the style. Also, he was a mentor for two other major figures of the classical period, Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart and Ludwig van Beethoven.

2.3 Op.20 String quartets

The *sun quartets* provided to be representative works of the string quartet genre, while remaining innovative to the compositional technique of string quartets. Among the reasons to use them in this work stands the interesting distribution of musical forms in their movements. As displayed in Table 1, within these string quartets there are sonata form movements, fugues, theme and variations, minuets and arias.

These string quartets also remain less experimental than later works, e.g., Op.33, which makes the task of automatic harmonic analysis suitable, without adding any further complications. Finally, musical resources such as syncopation, modulation, imitation and counterpoint are handled with mastery along these 24 pieces, which introduces different scenarios and test cases for an automatic harmonic analysis algorithm.

2.4 Creating the dataset

2.4.1 Finding and extending the musical scores

In order to create the dataset used in this work, I based in the current symbolic scores that can be found in the KernScores website [5]. This website already hosts

Missing movement
Op.20 No.1 - III. Affettuoso e sostenuto
Op.20 No.2 - II. Adagio
Op.20 No.3 - I. Allegro con Spirito
Op.20 No.4 - I. Allegro di Molto
Op.20 No.4 - II. Un poco Adagio Affettuoso

Table 2: Missing scores from Op.20 that are not available in the KernScores website

19 out of the 24 musical scores comprehending the Op.20 string quartets, so the effort left for having the entire Op.20 is to transcribe the musical pieces shown in Table 2 in a similar symbolic representation. These musical scores in KernScores are encoded in the *humdrum* format, which I will describe now.

2.4.2 About the Humdrum grammar

The *Humdrum* [3] grammar is a general-purpose grammar that allows to organize information in columns, called spines. However, it is probably almost exclusively used to encode musical information, using the ***kern* syntax. This syntax allows to write parts of a musical score, defining tempo, key signature, time signature, pitch and rhythm information. It is useful to encode this information in the ***kern* syntax as there are tools that extract and process this musical information, feeding the humdrum files into a computational musicology framework.

2.4.3 Manual annotations

Once the symbolic scores are complete, the next step in the creation of the dataset involves a manual harmonic analysis of each of the pieces. As presented during chapter 1, the expected output of the system is an annotated version in the form of a roman numeral analysis. Therefore, the manual analyses performed over the 24 pieces of the dataset have been done using these roman numeral analysis labels as well.

The best way to digitally append a roman numeral analysis to these symbolic scores is using the ***harm* syntax. which can be included as a spine in the humdrum file.

Original humdrum score				Appended analysis	
**kern	**kern	**kern	**kern	**harm	**commentary
*k[b-e-]	*k[b-e-]	*k[b-e-]	*k[b-e-]	*k[b-e-]	*k[b-e-]
*g:	*g:	*g:	*g:	*g:	*g:
*clefF4	*clefC3	*clefG2	*clefG2	*	*
*M3/4	*M3/4	*M3/4	*M3/4	*M3/4	*M3/4
2r	2r	2r	2r	.	.
4r	4r	4r	4d	.	.
1	1	1	1	1	1
4G	2.r	4B-	4b-	i	.
4A	.	4c	4a	iiio	Not really diminished, missing the fifth
4B-	.	4d	4g	ib	.
2	2	2	2	2	2
2c	2r	2e-	4g	iv	.
.	.	.	4g	.	.
4B-	4d	4d	4g	ib	.
3	3	3	3	3	3
[2.A	[2.c	[2.f#	4cc	viiob	.
.	.	.	4cc	.	.
.	.	.	4dd	V7c	.
4	4	4	4	4	4
2.A_	2.c_	2.f#_	2ee-	viiioD7b	.
.	.	.	4ee-	.	.
5	5	5	5	5	5
4A]	4c]	4f#]	4dd	V7c	.
2r	2r	2r	4r	.	.
.	.	.	4d	.	.

Table 3: Example of appending a manual annotation of roman numerals to a humdrum score

2.4.4 About the ****harm** syntax

The ***harm* [4] syntax is a dedicated syntax for annotating roman numerals, which is compatible with the Humdrum grammar. Among other things, it allows to represent different diatonic chords, as well as common chromatic substitutions in the common practice, e.g., augmented sixth and neapolitan chords. It also allows to set a current key to relate all the numeral degrees to, define a region as ambiguous in key, add intervals if a chord cannot be expressed with the roman numerals or chromatic substitution tokens.

Table 3 shows an example of appending this manual roman numeral analysis to the

same excerpt of music presented since the beginning of this document, i.e., *Joseph Haydn's Op.20 No.3 - II. Menuetto: Allegretto, mm.1-6*.

This example was taken from the dataset repository and thus this is how the annotations look in the dataset. The first appended column (spine, in the language of the humdrum grammar) represents the roman numeral labels, while the second is left for clarifications, explanations and any comment that is worth mentioning during certain point of the analysis. The only meaningful difference against the annotations in the dataset is that these have been prepended to the humdrum file instead of appended, as this allowed for easier parsing of the files.

In summary, as 19 out of 24 musical scores already exist in the KernScores website, it was a logical decision to complete the remaining pieces in the same format rather than starting a transcription effort from scratch. Once with the complete set of musical scores, a roman numeral analysis labeling has to be appended to these scores, one simple election to this purpose is the `**harm` syntax, comprehending roman numeral analysis and compatible with the humdrum grammar.

With this assumptions, now the automatic harmonic analysis system consists specifically of a humdrum score for input and the same humdrum score with an annotated `**harm` spine as the output. In the next chapter, I will discuss briefly the algorithms that have been developed for automatic harmonic analysis and to present the one used for this work.

Chapter 3

Literature review

During chapter 1, I defined what a system for automatic harmonic analysis consists of, i.e., *A piece of software that given a fragment of music as input, will output the same piece of music, with roman numeral labels appended to it.* At least for this particular work.

I also established during chapter 2 that the musical scores used for this work are encoded using the *Humdrum* [3] grammar and the roman numerals labeled using the ***harm* [4] syntax. In this chapter, I will go through a chronological list of attempts in conceiving a system of automatic harmonic analysis.

Aftwards, I will narrow the list of attempts, favoring the ones that could work with a musical score encoded in the humdrum grammar as input, and which can output a similar encoding with an appended ***harm* spine for the roman numeral labels.

Finally, I will discuss the selected attempt and the reason of its preference over other similarly suitable attempts.

3.1 Overview of Automatic Harmonic Analysis

3.1.1 The pioneer work by Terry Winograd

Researchers in the field mostly mention the approach from Terry Winograd [6], in 1968, as the pioneer work in the task of automatic harmonic analysis. This work is not only important because it is the first and pioneering work in computing a harmonic analysis, but also because it linked the computational techniques used in natural language processing to music. The model from Winograd was evaluated over music from Johann Sebastian Bach, and pretends to output a functional harmonic analysis of such pieces of music. To provide an output, it requires a preliminary hand-made conversion of the original score and turn it into a sequence of four-part perfect chords. This allowed him to process a score using his implementation in the LISP programming language, but it also means that during this pre-processing stage the non-harmonic tones are eliminated before solving the problem. In his 1997 harmonic analysis algorithm [7], David Temperley provided insight about the flaws of Winograd's model, among them he mentions the issues concerning melodic segregation and arpeggiations.

3.1.2 Expert system from Maxwell

A direct successor of Winograd's approach, the model from John Maxwell, which was part of his PhD dissertation in 1984, and successively published in 1992 [8], is probably the best example of the rule-based approaches towards harmonic analysis. Same as Winograd, Maxwell's target was to output a functional harmonic analysis from a music score. The model from Maxwell has fifty five rules that pretend to reduce the vertical sonorities into a chord sequence, and then deciding for key changes. Some of the rules are intuitive and basic, e.g.:

"Perfect and imperfect consonant intervals constitute a consonant interval. Every other is a dissonant interval.",

while others appear cryptic and difficult to understand, e.g.:

"If the goal chord falls on a strong beat and it is a major triad or major-minor seventh, and the root movement from the pre-cadence is an ascending or descending perfect fifth or major second or a descending minor second, and when the root motion is a descending fifth, the pre-cadence is not a potential dominant, and when the root motion is an ascending fifth the pre-cadence is triadic, then the pseudo-cadence is a half cadence, and its strength increases by 10. "

The later rule also reveals a problem that was pointed out by future researchers, the use of arbitrary, fixed values while determining the strength of a cadence.

Even so, the results of Maxwell's approach get really close to the outcome expected by a music theorist analyzing a music score and determining its functional harmony. This work was tested over three different movements of Johann Sebastian Bach's Six French Suites: The sarabande from Suite No.1, the menuet from Suite No.2 and the gavotte from Suite No.5. The pieces selected comprehend different problems and levels of complexity to be addressed: Four-part harmony with several non-harmonic tones, 2-voice continuous contrapuntual movement, and a varying contra-puntual texture, respectively. David Temperley listed the limitations of Winograd and Maxwell's approaches similarly, summarizing them in the following:

- Sequences of notes that are not displayed simultaneously (vertically), as arpeggiations of chords.
- Missing pitches in the spelling of a full chord, which can be deduced from the context.
- Ornamental notes. Maxwell proposes specific rules to deal with these notes, but according to Temperley, neither Maxwell's or Winograd's are good enough to correctly detect ornamental notes.

Maxwell's approach, in general, represents the powerful and sophisticated machinery of rule-based approaches, as well as their complexity.

3.1.3 Temperley and the Melisma Music Analyzer

Probably the most relevant approach in automatic harmonic analysis for this work, is the approach from David Temperley described in 1997 [7], as it was extended afterwards by his work in key estimation algorithms and which culminated in the implementation of the Melisma Music Analyzer, in conjunction with Daniel Sleator. Inspired by the cognitive experiments by Carol Krumhansl [9], the aim of Temperley is to produce an algorithm that models the human process of harmonic analysis done by a trained expert, and to take it as indicative of the analysis produced subconsciously by listeners in general.

The traditional functional harmonic analysis done in music theory courses uses the *roman numerals* notation to segment a piece of music, labeling it with symbols indicating the relationship between each root to the current key. Temperley steps forward in the definition of the problem of harmonic analysis, decomposing the task into two subtasks: *root finding* and *key finding*. Temperley claims then that functional harmonic analysis could be broken down into these subtasks, focusing at first in root finding, assuming that this task can be done independently to key finding. Root finding basically consists of dividing a piece into segments and label each of them with a root.

Once in the task of root-finding, Temperley approaches the task defining certain rules: *Pitch variance rule*, *compatibility rule*, *strong-beat rule*, *harmonic variance rule* and *ornamental dissonance rule*. Together with these rules, he introduces important definitions that aid in the process of root analysis: The concepts of *Tonal Pitch Class* (TPC), *Center of Gravity* (COG) and the *line of fifths*.

It is difficult to follow the chronology of this approach, as the implementation of this model comes mainly in the form of the Melisma Music Analyzer, which was released in 2001, and included the key estimation algorithm and a combined mode that eventually performed the complete functional harmonic analysis. The latest mode being the core implementation of what will be used to compute automatic harmonic analysis during this work.

3.1.4 Probabilistic and statistical approaches

Temperley himself, after the release of the Melisma Music Analyzer, moved into the direction of probabilistic models. In his case, using a Bayesian approach that aims to provide a unified modeling of harmonic analysis, meter induction and melodic segregation, challenging the individualization of these problems without considering the connections among them [10].

Another important probabilistic approach that emerged to solve the problem of functional harmonic analysis was that of Christopher Raphael [11]. This model from Raphael is one of the few pure-functional harmonic analysis approaches, oriented towards the analysis of common-practice music. The idea is simple and some of his assumptions simplify the parameters of the model. Some constant that remains as in previous models is the fact that it gets rid of all the pitch-spelling information and replaced for solely pitch information. This model, unlike Temperley, does not try to reconstruct the pitch spelling information back by any algorithmic means, and in the words of Raphael, it is an obvious extension to the model.

Another quite important effort in the statistical domain includes the work from Martin Rohrmeier [12], who uses a heuristic method of segmentation. Analyzes distributions of single pitch-class-sets, chord classes and pitch-class-sets transitions. One of the goals of Rohrmeier was the research of *syntacticality* in harmony. The final goal is to produce descriptive analyses of harmonic structure based on an empirical approach. The choice of the corpus is, similarly to others, music from Joahann Sebastian Bach. In his case, chorales, because they constitute a large and coherent set of pieces regarding style and composition technique. Rohrmeier claims that this work is pioneer in the statistical analysis of a corpus for the purpose of finding features of tonal harmony. According to the results of Rohrmeier, the most frequent occurrences of pitch-class-sets in this music are those of tonic, dominant and subdominant chords. This would be expected and helps to reinforce those scale-degree theories that describe harmonic movement with transition tables of scale degrees. The results from this research, apart from being interesting in confirming

music-theory beliefs regarding common chords and transitions in tonal music, could also be replicated in a different corpus to target its particular common chords and transitions.

3.1.5 Grammar-based

Three years after his statistical work in Bach Chorales, Martin Rohrmeier brought back the use of grammars to study the underlying structure of musical harmony [13], which inspired future works by other researchers in the field, specially towards analyzing jazz music. In this work, Rohrmeier claims that the structure of harmonic progressions exceeds the simplicity of a markovian transition table, and he proposes a set of phrase-structure grammar rules. For this purpose, the hierarchical analysis from the music-theory approach done by [14] is presented, with the belief that it can be brought to a closer formalization. Rohrmeier presents a tree representation of a chord sequence, using two principles:

- Chords have dependencies and the existence of one sometimes requires the existence of another
- Chords have functions, these functions can be realized by a set of chords.

The system comprises 27 rules for the generation of a grammar, this helps to model common-practice music as well as jazz music. The output of this algorithm is a hierarchical tree of the functions and dependencies of the chords. The level of detail from this work to model every special case of the harmonic language is remarkable, as careful attention has been put trying to comprehend distinct kinds of cadences, chords and modulations in the model.

This work was eventually retaken and implemented by Bas de Haas [15] using chord labels as input for the system.

As discussed previously, after I have overviewed the works in harmonic analysis, I will now narrow down the list of attempts that are most relevant to the expectations of this work. Among the most important factors that lead to separate the *favorite*

Approach	Year	Implementation	Availability
Winograd	1968	LISP	No
Maxwell	1992	LISP	No
Temperley	1997 ¹	C	Yes
Raphael	2003	C	Partial
Illescas	2008	Java	Partial

Table 4: Automatic functional harmonic analysis approaches

attempts from the rest, I could list two: The first one, being the capability of the system to deal with full scores as input, instead of a list of chord labels. The second, being the capability of the system to exploit, infer or reconstruct the pitch-spelling information from the original score in the output of the analyzed score.

3.2 Narrowing down the approaches

From the previously mentioned efforts of harmonic analysis, those that fit the best with the expected inputs and outputs of this work, are the following:

From the approaches shown in Table 4, I decided to choose the model and implementation from David Temperley’s algorithm to be run over the dataset of String Quartets Op.20.

The most important reason for this selection is because this is the approach with the most mature implementation, and the effort for getting humdrum scores to be analyzed using it is the minimum of all the other attempts.

Chapter 4

Methodology

As I described during chapter 3, the original model from David Temperley divided a system of automatic harmonic analysis in two subsystems: One that performs root detection and another one that performs key detection. Figure 5 shows how the core harmonic analysis of David Temperley comprises these two tasks.

Figure 5: Harmonic analysis as divided by David Temperley

However, thanks to the implementation work that has been already done by David Temperley, Daniel Sleator and Craig Sapp, the idea of using an implementation of this automatic harmonic analysis system over the dataset described in this work, which consists of musical scores encoded in humdrum files, is already feasible. During this chapter I will introduce the software stack, programs and scripts that allow for running an automatic harmonic analysis of a humdrum music score.

I will start from the analysis programs of the Melisma Music Analyzer, which are the

core of the analysis, to the scripts and programs of the Humdrum Extras software tools that allow for the use of real humdrum music scores.

4.1 The Melisma Music Analyzer

The Melisma Music Analyzer was implemented by Daniel Sleator over the work of David Temperley. It takes as input a *Notefile*, which could be said to be a plain-text representation of midi files. The Melisma Music Analyzer consists of several standalone programs, therefore, the output depends on the program that is being run over the *Notefile* input file. However, generally speaking, they all output a plain-text analysis of some sort.

In order to obtain a harmonic analysis, a Notefile needs to go through 3 stand-alone programs, one after another: Meter, Harmony and Key.

Figure 6: Melisma Music Analyzer, from a Notefile to a plain-text analysis

4.1.1 Meter

This program extracts metrical information about the musical piece, using the theories of the Generative Theory of Tonal Music as a basis. The output of this program is the same notefile with beat information appended at the end.

4.1.2 Harmony

This program takes as input the notefile with beat information (the output from the meter program), and outputs information about harmonic roots for each beat.

The name is somehow misleading, as this program's output is not harmony, but a harmonic root. Temperley divided the task of harmonic analysis in root estimation and key estimation, this program computing the first of these subtasks.

4.1.3 Key

This program takes as input the notefile with beat and harmonic-root information (the output from the harmony program). Something to remark about this program is that it might work with or without the information of the harmony program. In the first case, it performs a complete harmonic analysis. In the second case, it will only perform a key estimation.

Figure 6 shows the flow from an input Notefile to the plain-text analysis that is being output by the key estimation program of the Melisma Music Analyzer.

4.1.4 Problems with processing Notefile files

The input format from the Melisma Music Analyzer, yet it resembles a midi file, it is not a midi file. It is also not a standard type of file that could be encountered typically in other software. More important, it is incompatible with the humdrum encoding of the dataset used for this work, so at this point, we are unable to run an analysis over these musical scores.

However, there is one way around this problem. Using one of the programs found in the *Humdrum extras* collection.

4.2 Humdrum extras

The humdrum extras are a set of tools developed by Craig Sapp, mainly in the C++ programming language [16]. These tools are useful for additional processing of musical scores encoded in humdrum. For this work, I am particularly interested in a few of these utilities that help to pass a humdrum file to the melisma music analyzer, and then bring the output from melisma back to a humdrum representation.

Figure 7: Automatic harmonic analysis of a humdrum musical score

The first step is mitigating the problem around the Notefile format, for this, the *kern2melisma* program from the Humdrum Extras collection results quite useful.

4.2.1 kern2melisma

This program provides a parser to convert a humdrum file into the *Notefile* format used by Melisma. It is the first step in the workflow of a functional harmonic analysis from a humdrum score.

Once the input file is able to be processed over the programs of the Melisma Music Analyzer, it will be possible to obtain the plain-text analysis of the *Key* program. However, this analysis is difficult to parse as it is. Luckily, there is already a tool from the Humdrum Extras that provides help parsing this analysis, this tool is the *key2humdrum* script, written in PERL.

4.2.2 key2humdrum

This program takes the output from the *Key* program and outputs a pseudo-humdrum representation.

4.2.3 Appending to a humdrum file

The last step in getting the information back into a humdrum file is parsing the output of the *key2humdrum* program and appending this information to a humdrum spine. This process is not done by a standalone program, but rather a program that comprehends all the process described during this chapter. This program is called *tsroot*.

4.2.4 tsroot

The *tsroot* programs performs all the steps described before, starting from calling the *kern2melisma* to calling the Melisma programs and *key2humdrum*. Additionally, this program also interprets the output of *key2humdrum* and produces a final humdrum score with the analysis information appended to it.

Figure 7 could be seen as the process that happens each time the *tsroot* program is run over a humdrum score. This is a truthful realization of the target system for automatic harmonic analysis explained in the first chapters of this document.

Chapter 5

Evaluation

From all the implications of this work, probably the evaluation is the one that contributes some novelty to the task of automatic harmonic analysis.

During this chapter, I will introduce the evaluation process that I propose for validating how similar a manually annotated harmonic analysis stands compared to another generated automatically using the methods explained during chapter 4.

5.1 After the automatic analysis

So far, I reviewed the implementation efforts that materialize a system of automatic harmonic analysis which takes a musical score encoded in humdrum and outputs a similar musical score with roman numeral labels in the `**harm` syntax appended to it.

One important thing to know is that, together with the manual annotations described during chapter 2, all the automatic analyses for the musical scores used in this work have been also saved in the same repository where the manual annotations are contained.

This means, in summary, that the repository (https://github.com/napulen/haydn_op20_harm) where the dataset lives holds manual and automatic annotations for the musical scores.

Manual analysis		Automatic analysis	
**harm	**root	**harm	**root
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
.	.	.	.
=1	=1	=1	=1
i	g	.	.
.	.	.	.
iiio	a	iv	f
.	.	.	.
ib	g	.	.
.	.	.	.
=2	=2	=2	=2
iv	c	ib	c
.	.	.	.
.	.	V7c	g
.	.	.	.
ib	g	.	.
.	.	.	.

Table 5: Sample evaluation file.

Now, I will describe the process of putting together both, the manual and automatic harmonic analysis annotations into a single file. A single file that can then be used to compare the similarity of the analyses. I call this file, the evaluation file.

5.2 Evaluation file

The evaluation file is a valid humdrum file with four spines.

The first pair of spines represents the roman numeral and harmonic root of the manual analysis, while the second represents the corresponding elements of the automatic analysis.

Table 5 provides a first glance at a fragment of an evaluation file, extracted from the first two measures of the second movement of the String Quartet Op.20 No.3.

The first characteristic I want to discuss about this evaluation file, is its normaliza-

Measure	Analysis 1		Analysis 2	
Anacrusis

First measure	i	g	.	.
	iio	a	iv	f
	ib	g	.	.
Second measure	iv	c	ib	c
	.	.	V7c	g
	ib	g	.	.

Table 6: Original time units

tion of time units.

5.2.1 Normalization of time units

If the evaluation file displayed before would keep the original time units of the labels, it would look like as shown in Table 6.

One problem that arises with the way ****harm** spines are appended to the scores, is that these spines do not store any explicit information about time duration. The labels are properly interpreted in the full score because they are aligned to the note values from the ****kern** spines, which do have time duration information.

In order to avoid this and other problems related to duration, during the creation of the evaluation file, the time units of the score get normalized to the shortest note of the score.

5.2.2 Finding the shortest note

In order to find the shortest note, the *census* program is being used, which is part of the *Humdrum Toolkit* [3].

Table 7 shows the output of the *census* program for the humdrum file of the second movement of Op.20 No.3. Among the output of the *KERN DATA* section, the duration of the shortest note of the humdrum score is displayed. This note duration is parsed from the output of the program and used to make a new timebase for the evaluation file.

HUMDRUM DATA

Number of data tokens:	1780
Number of null tokens:	515
Number of multiple-stops:	1
Number of data records:	445
Number of comments:	27
Number of interpretations:	7
Number of records:	479

KERN DATA

Number of note-heads:	785
Number of notes:	741
Longest note:	2
Shortest note:	8
Highest note:	ddd
Lowest note:	DD
Number of rests:	125
Maximum number of voices:	5
Number of single barlines:	88
Number of double barlines:	1

Table 7: Output from the census program of the Humdrum Toolkit

Measure	Analysis 1		Analysis 2	
Anacrusis

First	i	g	.	.

	ii \bar{o}	a	iv	f

	ib	g	.	.

Second	iv	c	ib	c

	.	.	V7c	g

	ib	g	.	.

Table 8: Setting time units normalization to the evaluation file

As a matter of explanation, the string value that appears as the shortest note is in the frequently used reciprocal notation. In this case, a value of "8" means the note duration is 1/8 of a whole note, or an eight note. Basically, as this example holds a time signature of 3/4 and the shortest note is an eight note, six eight notes are expected for every measure.

Table 8 shows precisely this, the normalized evaluation file, six entries per measure, each of them corresponding to an eight note, the shortest note of the music score.

5.3 Computing a result from an evaluation file

Once the contents and characteristics of an evaluation file have been described, now I will describe the process of comparing between both analyses contained in this file to obtain a final result of similarity between the analyses.

Time unit	How it is written		How it is interpreted	
	Root 1	Root 2	Root 1	Root 2
1
2
3
4
5
6
7	g	.	g	.
8	.	.	g	.
9	a	f	a	f
10	.	.	a	f
11	g	.	g	f
12	.	.	g	f
13	c	c	c	c
14	.	.	c	c
15	.	g	c	g
16	.	.	c	g
17	g	.	g	g
18	.	.	g	g

Table 9: Root spines, the 2nd and 4th spines of an evaluation file

5.3.1 Comparing root spines

The comparison process could be summarized simply as counting the number of string matches between the second and fourth spines of the evaluation file, with some minor considerations.

As long as one root appears in one of the spines, it will be considered the "current" root, meaning that any *NULL* record (a record with a dot in it) is considered to be of the same root as the last one appearing in the spine.

This becomes clearer from looking at Table 9. The *NULL* records are replaced by the last root that appeared in the spine.

After this assumption has been explained, the next step is simply comparing the roots from both analyses, row by row.

Time unit	Root 1	Root 2	Match
1	.	.	Yes
2	.	.	Yes
3	.	.	Yes
4	.	.	Yes
5	.	.	Yes
6	.	.	Yes
7	g	.	No
8	g	.	No
9	a	f	No
10	a	f	No
11	g	f	No
12	g	f	No
13	c	c	Yes
14	c	c	Yes
15	c	g	No
16	c	g	No
17	g	g	No
18	g	g	No

Table 10: Matching the root spines from an evaluation file

5.3.2 Harmonic roots

Little has been said about the ****root** elements corresponding to the second and fourth spines, and where have they been obtained from.

These roots are computed by using *harm2kern*, another tool from Humdrum Extras [16]. The idea behind using these *root* values in the evaluation, instead of for example, a raw string comparison between the roman numerals, is to resolve the ambiguity that is caused by possible different tonalities in the harmonic analyses.

Due to the nature of roman numerals, they might be representing something similar in context, but quite different in spelling, these roots pretend to "normalize" a roman numeral label and resolve it into a single letter.

There are of course drawbacks out of this approach, the most important of them being that if the analysis considers changes in tonality during the music score, these are ignored. Ideally, this changes in tonality should not be ignored, and they comprehend an important part of the analysis, however, proposing an evaluation process

that incorporates these changes in tonality is rather difficult, and it is proposed as one of the key aspects to improve in future work.

Finally, Table 10 displays the evaluation summary for the first two measures (and anacrusis) of the example shown at the beginning of the chapter. This example consists of 18 time units, 8 of them matching. However, only 2 of them really match due to their root value, the rest are simply the initial padding of NULL records.

Chapter 6

Results

Using the mentioned procedure for evaluation, Table 11 shows the results for each of the 24 movements in Op.24.

Another interesting to notice is that, in general, the automatic analysis generates more chord labels than the one annotated manually. Tables 12 to 17 show the chord distributions for the entire Op.20, in both cases, the manual and automatic annotations.

Movement	Matching time units	Total time units	Score
Op.20 No.1			
I	2261	3489	64,80%
II	221	805	27,45%
III	1319	1730	76,24%
IV	332	1289	25,76%
Op.20 No.2			
I	1254	5137	24,41%
II	1119	2017	55,48%
III	713	1033	69,02%
IV	309	1945	15,89%
Op.20 No.3			
I	2426	4322	56,13%
II	121	535	22,62%
III	3386	4069	83,21%
IV	535	1681	31,83%
Op.20 No.4			
I	2464	3663	67,27%
II	1992	3922	50,79%
III	65	223	29,15%
IV	1651	6289	26,25%
Op.20 No.5			
I	4950	7729	64,04%
II	793	1201	66,03%
III	2617	3061	85,49%
IV	798	1473	54,18%
Op.20 No.6			
I	1808	3985	45,37%
II	6217	7585	81,96%
III	405	505	80,20%
IV	1361	3041	44,76%

Table 11: Results for the evaluation of the Haydn's Op.20 dataset

Op.20 No.1 1st movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	Op.20 No.1 3rd movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation		
	I	38 (24.36%)			I	50 (23.47%)			
	VI	11 (7.05%)			VI	18 (8.45%)			
	VII	12 (7.69%)			VII	15 (7.04%)			
	N	1 (0.64%)			IV	17 (7.98%)			
	II	16 (10.26%)			II	19 (8.92%)			
	V	67 (42.95%)			V	79 (37.09%)			
	IV	9 (5.77%)			GN	4 (1.88%)			
	III	2 (1.28%)			III	11 (5.16%)			
	Total	156			Total	213			
	Root	Number of chords			Automatic annotation	Root		Number of chords	Automatic annotation
	I	133 (32.13%)				I		69 (30.80%)	
	VI	19 (4.59%)				VI		17 (7.59%)	
	VII	1 (0.24%)				VII		4 (1.79%)	
IV	52 (12.56%)	IV	32 (14.29%)						
II	72 (17.39%)	II	36 (16.07%)						
V	129 (31.16%)	V	65 (29.02%)						
III	8 (1.93%)	III	1 (0.45%)						
Total	414	Total	224						
Op.20 No.1 2nd movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	Op.20 No.1 4th movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation		
	I	24 (31.58%)			I	49 (25.39%)			
	VII	8 (10.53%)			VI	5 (2.59%)			
	IV	11 (14.47%)			VII	28 (14.51%)			
	II	5 (6.58%)			IV	16 (8.29%)			
	LT	2 (2.63%)			II	5 (2.59%)			
	V	26 (34.21%)			V	80 (41.45%)			
	Total	76			GN	2 (1.04%)			
	Root	Number of chords			Automatic annotation	Root		Number of chords	Automatic annotation
	I	28 (34.57%)				I		81 (29.35%)	
II	8 (9.88%)	VI	12 (4.35%)						
VI	3 (3.70%)	VII	2 (0.72%)						
IV	10 (12.35%)	IV	34 (12.32%)						
V	32 (39.51%)	II	41 (14.86%)						
Total	81	V	102 (36.96%)						
			III	4 (1.45%)	Total	276			

Table 12: Chord distributions for Op.20 No.1

Op.20 No.2 1st movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	Op.20 No.2 3rd movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	
	I	48 (22.22%)			I	27 (28.72%)		
	VI	15 (6.94%)			VI	4 (4.26%)		
	VII	23 (10.65%)			VII	12 (12.77%)		
	IV	17 (7.87%)			IV	10 (10.64%)		
	II	12 (5.56%)			II	2 (2.13%)		
	V	89 (41.20%)			V	37 (39.36%)		
	GN	2 (0.93%)			III	2 (2.13%)		
	N	1 (0.46%)			Total	94		
	III	9 (4.17%)			Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation
	Total	216			I	42 (32.81%)		
	Root	Number of chords			VI	3 (2.34%)		
	I	77 (26.37%)			VII	3 (2.34%)		
	VI	18 (6.16%)			IV	29 (22.66%)		
VII	1 (0.34%)	II	11 (8.59%)					
IV	42 (14.38%)	V	38 (29.69%)					
II	29 (9.93%)	III	2 (1.56%)					
V	120 (41.10%)	Total	128					
III	5 (1.71%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
Total	292	I	79 (18.90%)					
Root	Number of chords	VI	37 (8.85%)					
I	36 (23.08%)	VII	52 (12.44%)					
VI	8 (5.13%)	IV	48 (11.48%)					
VII	15 (9.62%)	II	40 (9.57%)					
IV	23 (14.74%)	LT	5 (1.20%)					
II	7 (4.49%)	V	138 (33.01%)					
V	61 (39.10%)	GN	1 (0.24%)					
III	6 (3.85%)	III	18 (4.31%)					
Total	156	Total	418					
Op.20 No.2 2nd movement	Root	Number of chords	Automatic annotation	Op.20 No.2 4th movement	Root	Number of chords	Automatic annotation	
	I	55 (26.96%)			I	101 (19.65%)		
	VI	8 (3.92%)			VI	42 (8.17%)		
	VII	7 (3.43%)			VII	10 (1.95%)		
	IV	42 (20.59%)			IV	49 (9.53%)		
	II	17 (8.33%)			II	88 (17.12%)		
	V	67 (32.84%)			V	206 (40.08%)		
	III	8 (3.92%)			III	18 (3.50%)		
	Total	204			Total	514		

Table 13: Chord distributions for Op.20 No.2

Op.20 No.3 1st movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	Op.20 No.3 3rd movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	
	I	51 (15.94%)			I	62 (36.26%)		
	VI	22 (6.88%)			VI	8 (4.68%)		
	VII	33 (10.31%)			VII	3 (1.75%)		
	IV	35 (10.94%)			IV	16 (9.36%)		
	II	21 (6.56%)			II	6 (3.51%)		
	LT	10 (3.12%)			V	73 (42.69%)		
	V	128 (40.00%)			GN	1 (0.58%)		
	GN	2 (0.62%)			III	2 (1.17%)		
	N	3 (0.94%)			Total	171		
	III	15 (4.69%)			Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation
	Total	320			I	68 (36.56%)		
	Root	Number of chords			VI	6 (3.23%)		
	I	128 (27.47%)			IV	35 (18.82%)		
VI	28 (6.01%)	II	7 (3.76%)					
VII	12 (2.58%)	V	66 (35.48%)					
IV	65 (13.95%)	III	4 (2.15%)					
II	57 (12.23%)	Total	186					
V	153 (32.83%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
III	23 (4.94%)	I	48 (29.63%)					
Total	466	VI	10 (6.17%)					
Root	Number of chords	VII	20 (12.35%)					
I	31 (21.23%)	N	2 (1.23%)					
VI	6 (4.11%)	II	3 (1.85%)					
VII	20 (13.70%)	V	62 (38.27%)					
IV	9 (6.16%)	GN	2 (1.23%)					
II	11 (7.53%)	IV	10 (6.17%)					
LT	1 (0.68%)	III	5 (3.09%)					
V	63 (43.15%)	Total	162					
N	1 (0.68%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
III	4 (2.74%)	I	77 (34.68%)					
Total	146	VI	7 (3.15%)					
Root	Number of chords	VII	2 (0.90%)					
I	44 (30.14%)	IV	29 (13.06%)					
VI	5 (3.42%)	II	15 (6.76%)					
VII	2 (1.37%)	V	87 (39.19%)					
IV	16 (10.96%)	III	5 (2.25%)					
II	23 (15.75%)	Total	222					
V	51 (34.93%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
III	5 (3.42%)	I	20 (30.77%)					
Total	146	VI	5 (7.69%)					
Root	Number of chords	VII	4 (6.15%)					
I	111 (32.17%)	IV	3 (4.62%)					
VI	5 (1.45%)	II	8 (12.31%)					
VII	40 (11.59%)	V	25 (38.46%)					
IV	39 (11.30%)	GN	2 (0.58%)					
II	35 (10.14%)	N	1 (0.29%)					
V	101 (29.28%)	III	11 (3.19%)					
GN	2 (0.58%)	Total	345					
N	1 (0.29%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
III	11 (3.19%)	I	132 (30.14%)					
Total	438	VI	23 (5.25%)					
Root	Number of chords	VII	1 (0.23%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	IV	54 (12.33%)					
VI	21 (8.05%)	II	61 (13.93%)					
VII	46 (17.62%)	V	156 (35.62%)					
IV	37 (14.18%)	III	11 (2.51%)					
II	5 (1.92%)	Total	261					
V	61 (23.37%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
GN	7 (2.68%)	I	87 (31.52%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	VI	6 (2.17%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	VII	10 (3.62%)					
Total	261	IV	58 (21.01%)					
Root	Number of chords	II	16 (5.80%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	V	91 (32.97%)					
VI	21 (8.05%)	III	8 (2.90%)					
VII	46 (17.62%)	Total	276					
IV	37 (14.18%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
II	5 (1.92%)	I	101 (33.22%)					
V	61 (23.37%)	VI	10 (3.29%)					
GN	7 (2.68%)	VII	5 (1.64%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	IV	34 (11.18%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	II	51 (16.78%)					
Total	261	V	89 (29.28%)					
Root	Number of chords	III	14 (4.61%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	Total	304					
VI	21 (8.05%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
VII	46 (17.62%)	I	82 (27.06%)					
IV	37 (14.18%)	VI	11 (3.63%)					
II	5 (1.92%)	VII	30 (9.90%)					
V	61 (23.37%)	IV	28 (9.24%)					
GN	7 (2.68%)	II	40 (13.20%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	LT	3 (0.99%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	V	96 (31.68%)					
Total	261	GN	4 (1.32%)					
Root	Number of chords	III	9 (2.97%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	Total	303					
VI	21 (8.05%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
VII	46 (17.62%)	I	101 (33.22%)					
IV	37 (14.18%)	VI	10 (3.29%)					
II	5 (1.92%)	VII	5 (1.64%)					
V	61 (23.37%)	IV	34 (11.18%)					
GN	7 (2.68%)	II	51 (16.78%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	V	89 (29.28%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	III	14 (4.61%)					
Total	261	Total	304					

Table 14: Chord distributions for Op.20 No.3

Op.20 No.4 1st movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	Op.20 No.4 3rd movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	
	I	111 (32.17%)			I	20 (30.77%)		
	VI	5 (1.45%)			VI	5 (7.69%)		
	VII	40 (11.59%)			VII	4 (6.15%)		
	IV	39 (11.30%)			IV	3 (4.62%)		
	II	35 (10.14%)			II	8 (12.31%)		
	V	101 (29.28%)			V	25 (38.46%)		
	GN	2 (0.58%)			Total	65		
	N	1 (0.29%)			Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation
	III	11 (3.19%)			I	18 (33.96%)		
	Total	345			II	9 (16.98%)		
	Root	Number of chords			VI	1 (1.89%)		
	I	132 (30.14%)			V	20 (37.74%)		
	VI	23 (5.25%)			IV	5 (9.43%)		
VII	1 (0.23%)	Total	53					
IV	54 (12.33%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
II	61 (13.93%)	I	82 (27.06%)					
V	156 (35.62%)	VI	11 (3.63%)					
III	11 (2.51%)	VII	30 (9.90%)					
Total	438	IV	28 (9.24%)					
Root	Number of chords	II	40 (13.20%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	LT	3 (0.99%)					
VI	21 (8.05%)	V	96 (31.68%)					
VII	46 (17.62%)	GN	4 (1.32%)					
IV	37 (14.18%)	III	9 (2.97%)					
II	5 (1.92%)	Total	303					
V	61 (23.37%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
GN	7 (2.68%)	I	101 (33.22%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	VI	10 (3.29%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	VII	5 (1.64%)					
Total	261	IV	34 (11.18%)					
Root	Number of chords	II	51 (16.78%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	V	89 (29.28%)					
VI	21 (8.05%)	III	14 (4.61%)					
VII	46 (17.62%)	Total	304					
IV	37 (14.18%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
II	5 (1.92%)	I	82 (27.06%)					
V	61 (23.37%)	VI	11 (3.63%)					
GN	7 (2.68%)	VII	30 (9.90%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	IV	28 (9.24%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	II	40 (13.20%)					
Total	261	LT	3 (0.99%)					
Root	Number of chords	V	96 (31.68%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	GN	4 (1.32%)					
VI	21 (8.05%)	III	9 (2.97%)					
VII	46 (17.62%)	Total	303					
IV	37 (14.18%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
II	5 (1.92%)	I	101 (33.22%)					
V	61 (23.37%)	VI	10 (3.29%)					
GN	7 (2.68%)	VII	5 (1.64%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	IV	34 (11.18%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	II	51 (16.78%)					
Total	261	V	89 (29.28%)					
Root	Number of chords	III	14 (4.61%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	Total	304					
VI	21 (8.05%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
VII	46 (17.62%)	I	82 (27.06%)					
IV	37 (14.18%)	VI	11 (3.63%)					
II	5 (1.92%)	VII	30 (9.90%)					
V	61 (23.37%)	IV	28 (9.24%)					
GN	7 (2.68%)	II	40 (13.20%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	LT	3 (0.99%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	V	96 (31.68%)					
Total	261	GN	4 (1.32%)					
Root	Number of chords	III	9 (2.97%)					
I	60 (22.99%)	Total	303					
VI	21 (8.05%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
VII	46 (17.62%)	I	101 (33.22%)					
IV	37 (14.18%)	VI	10 (3.29%)					
II	5 (1.92%)	VII	5 (1.64%)					
V	61 (23.37%)	IV	34 (11.18%)					
GN	7 (2.68%)	II	51 (16.78%)					
N	8 (3.07%)	V	89 (29.28%)					
III	16 (6.13%)	III	14 (4.61%)					
Total	261	Total	304					

Table 15: Chord distributions for Op.20 No.4

Op.20 No.5 1st movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	Op.20 No.5 3rd movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	
	I	68 (29.18%)			I	49 (25.79%)		
	VI	6 (2.58%)			VI	13 (6.84%)		
	VII	15 (6.44%)			VII	12 (6.32%)		
	IV	19 (8.15%)			IV	9 (4.74%)		
	II	22 (9.44%)			II	24 (12.63%)		
	V	94 (40.34%)			V	82 (43.16%)		
	GN	4 (1.72%)			III	1 (0.53%)		
	III	5 (2.15%)			Total	190		
	Total	233			Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation
	I	160 (31.87%)			I	65 (30.95%)		
	VI	10 (1.99%)			VI	14 (6.67%)		
	VII	9 (1.79%)			IV	20 (9.52%)		
	IV	72 (14.34%)			II	30 (14.29%)		
II	47 (9.36%)	V	81 (38.57%)					
V	195 (38.84%)	Total	210					
III	9 (1.79%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
Total	502	I	71 (28.74%)					
I	43 (28.29%)	VI	16 (6.48%)					
VI	7 (4.61%)	VII	34 (13.77%)					
VII	26 (17.11%)	IV	24 (9.72%)					
IV	12 (7.89%)	II	9 (3.64%)					
II	6 (3.95%)	V	89 (36.03%)					
LT	2 (1.32%)	III	4 (1.62%)					
V	48 (31.58%)	Total	247					
GN	1 (0.66%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
III	7 (4.61%)	I	92 (26.98%)					
Total	152	VI	14 (4.11%)					
I	55 (37.67%)	VII	3 (0.88%)					
VI	2 (1.37%)	IV	66 (19.35%)					
IV	22 (15.07%)	II	21 (6.16%)					
II	8 (5.48%)	V	137 (40.18%)					
V	56 (38.36%)	III	8 (2.35%)					
III	3 (2.05%)	Total	341					
Total	146							

Table 16: Chord distributions for Op.20 No.5

Op.20 No.6 1st movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	Op.20 No.6 3rd movement	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation	
	I	98 (33.68%)			I	26 (41.27%)		
	VI	13 (4.47%)			VI	1 (1.59%)		
	VII	17 (5.84%)			VII	3 (4.76%)		
	IV	22 (7.56%)			IV	8 (12.70%)		
	II	18 (6.19%)			II	2 (3.17%)		
	LT	2 (0.69%)			V	22 (34.92%)		
	V	117 (40.21%)			III	1 (1.59%)		
	GN	2 (0.69%)			Total	63		
	III	2 (0.69%)			Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation
	Total	291			I	27 (45.00%)		
	I	146 (36.50%)			II	1 (1.67%)		
	VI	15 (3.75%)			VI	1 (1.67%)		
	VII	6 (1.50%)			IV	12 (20.00%)		
IV	60 (15.00%)	V	19 (31.67%)					
II	15 (3.75%)	Total	60					
V	155 (38.75%)	Root	Number of chords	Manual annotation				
III	3 (0.75%)	I	66 (23.74%)					
Total	400	VI	30 (10.79%)					
I	49 (26.20%)	VII	14 (5.04%)					
VI	8 (4.28%)	IV	25 (8.99%)					
VII	24 (12.83%)	II	36 (12.95%)					
IV	13 (6.95%)	V	90 (32.37%)					
II	8 (4.28%)	GN	1 (0.36%)					
V	81 (43.32%)	III	16 (5.76%)					
GN	1 (0.53%)	Total	278					
III	3 (1.60%)	Root	Number of chords		Automatic annotation			
Total	187	I	66 (19.64%)					
I	53 (31.18%)	VI	38 (11.31%)					
VI	6 (3.53%)	VII	6 (1.79%)					
IV	31 (18.24%)	IV	24 (7.14%)					
II	15 (8.82%)	II	60 (17.86%)					
V	61 (35.88%)	V	111 (33.04%)					
III	4 (2.35%)	III	31 (9.23%)					
Total	170	Total	336					

Table 17: Chord distributions for Op.20 No.6

Chapter 7

Discussion

7.1 Conclusions

Even though the baseline model for this work is the algorithm by David Temperley from 1997, a lot can be said about the process of going from a raw music score encoded in Humdrum to an analyzed version of the same score. The source code used to compute these analyses comes from different persons, different years and different programming languages (e.g.: C, C++, Perl, Bash and Python).

It is easy to assume that the work of a researcher could end in providing a model to solve a problem, but much more comes into place in trying to use this model for bigger volumes of information. I believe this is the real finality of this work, to provide insight and feedback in the experience of *setting up* the analysis of a considerable amount of music, using one model from 1997 in the core of all that, necessary mountain of software programs.

7.2 Future work

Among the ideas that stand very clear of what can be improved, I can list two: Extending the dataset and improving the evaluation.

7.2.1 Adding content to the dataset

Joseph Haydn is a very important composer from the Classical Period, so are two other composers that could be considered his pupils: Ludwig van Beethoven and Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart. Both of them wrote string quartets, inspired in the work from Haydn. Particularly, I am interested in adding these sets of string quartets to the dataset.

- Beethoven's Six String Quartets Op.18.
- Mozart's Six String Quartets Op.10.

Each of this opus contains 6 string quartets, similar to the Op.20 of Joseph Haydn used for this work. Both of them stand relevant in the history of the string quartet.

7.2.2 Improved evaluation

I mentioned the process I followed for "normalizing" the roman numeral labels during the evaluation process, and the drawbacks of this approach.

During this work, I have been constructing a parser of `**harm` expressions based on regular expressions. This parser allows for extracting critical information out of a roman numeral label in the `**harm` syntax. This information is intended to be used for improving the evaluation process.

The current version of this parser is located in this repository:

<https://github.com/napulen/harmparser>

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Appendix A

Bugs and Bugfixes

This section describes different issues presented and addressed during this work

A.1 Transcription issues

A.1.1 Transcription of the missing files from Op.20

- Op.20 No.4 - I: mm.127 Replacing E in the first beat of the second violin, for E#

A.1.2 Corrections over the Altmann Edition

- Op.20 No.2 - I: mm.29 In the Altmann edition, the bass goes to E flat after a Dominant Seventh chord, however, in other editions it moves to the tonic, it makes more sense to the harmonic context to move towards the tonic, therefore, ignoring the spelling of the Altmann Edition for this measure and considering the bass as heading to the tonic in the third beat of the measure.

A.1.3 Corrections over previous KernScores corpus

- Op.20 No.4 - I: mm.124 Changing the spelling of the viola from F natural to E sharp as it explains better a dominant seventh chord, and also, it appears

like that in the Altmann Edition.

- Op.20 No.4 - IV: mm.24 Adding an e natural to the first violin. It matches what is written in the Altmann Edition, and it makes the harmony clearer, from a g-diminished triad to a fully diminished e natural seventh chord, which explains better the f chord in the next measure
- Op.20 No.4 - IV: mm.92 & mm.94 Correcting wrong spelling of a note in the viola
- Op.20 No.6 - II: mm.5 Changing the D in the fourth beat of the measure for a B natural, which matches the Altmann Edition

A.2 Annotation issues

A.2.1 Corner cases

- Op.20 No.4 - IV: mm.6 "The augmented triad on the fifth scale degree may be used as a substitute dominant, and may also be considered as bIII+, for example in C: V+ = G-B-D#, bIII+ = Eb-G-B, and since in every key D# = Eb, they are the same three pitches.", *Theories and Practice of Harmonic Analysis*. p. 35. ISBN 0-7734-9917-2.

A.2.2 Non-expert analysis

Most of the analyses were done by me, I am not an expert.

A.2.3 Fugues are too contrapunctual

The fourth movements of Op.20 No.2, No.5 and No.6 are fugues, these were some of the most difficult scores to analyze manually, mainly because they are very contrapunctual.

A.2.4 Flat -VII annotated as VII

While annotating the scores, I marked the lowered seventh degree of the minor mode simply as VII, while it should be a lowered seventh -VII. It could affect the results.

A.3 Workflow issues

A.3.1 Source code coming from different sources

The main problem is that the source code comes from different repositories, and it is difficult in terms of reproducibility to put everything together in one place and guarantee it will work.

A.3.2 Melisma array sizes

There was an "error" in the melisma music analyzer. The size of static structures like arrays, have been hardcoded, in long scores like Op.20 No.3 - I, the program reached buffer overflow and crashed without completing the analysis, I fixed my version of the Melisma Music Analyzer programs to correct this, but this code is not public, as I am not aware of the license of the Melisma source code. If attempting to run the analysis in these files, the programs will crash unless this is fixed.

- Op.20 No.4 - IV
- Op.20 No.3 - I
- Op.20 No.5- I

A.3.3 tsroot harmony2humdrum and key2humdrum

tsroot had a different default tempo than kern2melisma, therefore, when running the analysis over files with no explicit tempo information, the result is incorrect. I fixed this in my version of the humdrum extra tools, you can download it from my fork repository. At the moment of this publication, the fix for this has not been merged in the main project repository.

A.4 Evaluation issues

A.4.1 Chr chords are ignored

I am ignoring the annotations denoted as *Chr* by the automatic analysis, instead of denoting a change of harmony after encountering this tag, I am preserving the previous harmonic root. This is probably wrong and should be addressed in a future evaluation.

A.4.2 Resolution of degree in secondary functions

Though I described the process to resolve a subfunction, I did not write this code with my harmparser. In practice, I delegated this process to the harm2kern program that is already available in the humdrum extra tools. I did not check if the parser from harm2kern is doing this process as I described it. It might be somewhat different.

A.5 Bugfixes

As the result of this work, a few problems were addressed

A.5.1 tsroot `-meldir` and `-midir` args

The implementation of tsroot has a hardcoded default value of the meldir and midir directories, when trying to change it with console arguments, the program crashed as there was some issue in the translation of the C string. This problem was detected and now it is corrected in the latest version of humdrum extras. Special thanks to Craig Sapp who double-checked this after I posted in the humdrum forum

A.5.2 tsroot tempo correction

As stated previously, there is a different default tempo in the tsroot program than the kern2melisma program, this means if a file has not an explicit tempo indication,

the output analysis is incorrect. This was the case for the entire dataset of Op.20, so detecting and correcting this issue was crucial for this work. This fix has not been until this point merged into the official humdrum extra repository.